

Lymphatic PD-L1 regulates PD-1+ CD8+ and CD4+ T cells infiltrating immune checkpoint-sensitive melanoma

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Abstract

Lymph node (LN)-resident lymphatic endothelial cells (LECs) form a critical interphase between the lymphatic sinus lumen and the LN parenchyma. Beyond their role in leukocyte trafficking, LECs shape immune responses as they scavenge and (cross-) present exogenous antigens and constitutively express immune-regulatory proteins such as PD-L1. However, it remains unclear which immune cell types and activation states are sensitive to LN lymphatic PD-L1, and whether lymphatic PD-L1 expression impacts sensitivity to immune checkpoint blockade (ICB) in cancer therapy. To dissect the contribution of LN lymphatic PD-L1 to tumor immunity in melanoma, we utilized a conditional lymphatic PD-L1 knock-out mouse model in combination with syngeneic mouse melanoma models varying in ICB sensitivity. While lymphatic PD-L1 deletion did not alter tumor growth or the immune landscape within tdLNs, it modulated the intratumoral immune composition in ICB-sensitive but not in ICB-resistant melanoma. Specifically, lymphatic PD-L1 deletion resulted in an increased frequency of proliferative PD-1⁺ CD8⁺ progenitor exhausted T cells and a reduction in PD-1⁺ Th1 T cells. Together, our findings reveal that lymphatic PD-L1 plays a context-dependent role in shaping anti-tumor T cell responses, particularly in ICB-sensitive disease.

Introduction

Immune checkpoint blockade (ICB) was initially conceived to reinvigorate exhausted T cells in the tumor microenvironment (TME) and restore anti-tumor effector functions.¹ However, accumulating evidence indicates that ICB exerts effects not only within the TME but also at regional and systemic levels.^{2,3} In particular, tumor-draining LNs (tdLNs) have

emerged as critical sites of action in ICB therapy. Notably, lymphadenectomy performed in mice prior to ICB treatment abolishes its therapeutic efficacy, underscoring the importance of tdLNs in mediating treatment responses.^{3,4} Moreover, localized administration of ICB to tdLNs yields equal or superior tumor control compared to systemic treatment.⁵⁻⁷ Several studies have identified early-stage CD8⁺ T cells within tdLNs as direct responders to ICB. By expressing TCF1 and maintaining strong proliferative and self-renewal capacities, these cells generate a robust pool of TCF1⁺ TOX⁺ progenitor exhausted T cells (T_{pex}) that subsequently migrate to the TME.^{3,8}

LNs are essential for generating adaptive immune responses as well as peripheral tolerance.^{9,10} They consist of diverse immune and stromal cell populations, including lymphatic endothelial cells (LECs). Interestingly, LECs can scavenge and cross-present exogenous antigens on MHC-I molecules. LECs also express MHC-II molecules, and constitutively express immune checkpoint proteins such as programmed death ligand 1 (PD-L1, CD274), while lacking co-stimulatory molecules, suggesting a potential role in immune suppression.¹⁰⁻¹⁵ PD-L1 mRNA is robustly expressed by LN LECs, specifically within subcapsular sinus floor (fLEC) and medullary sinus (mLEC) subsets, in contrast to peripheral LECs where PD-L1 is absent in steady-state conditions and is only upregulated under inflammation.¹⁶⁻¹⁹ Importantly, due to their location, LN LECs are in close contact with migrating and resident immune cells, potentially influencing a broad spectrum of immune responses. For example, PD-L1⁺ fLECs and mLECs closely interact with sinusoidal macrophages and dendritic cells. Moreover, circulating immune cells must transmigrate across these LEC layers to enter the LN parenchyma from the subcapsular sinus or to exit the LN parenchyma via efferent lymphatics.

We previously demonstrated that lymphatic PD-L1 promotes the apoptosis of tumor antigen-specific CD8⁺ T cells with a CD44⁺ CD62L⁺ central memory (T_{cm}) phenotype in mouse models of ICB-sensitive colorectal carcinoma (MC38) and ICB-resistant melanoma (B16-F10), implicating LN LEC PD-L1 in tumor immune evasion.²⁰ However, the precise nature of immune cells sensitive to lymphatic PD-L1 in tdLNs and the TME in relation to tumor ICB responsiveness has remained elusive. Furthermore, while LN LECs express PD-L1 mRNA in both mice and humans, the presence of PD-L1 protein in human LN LECs has not been investigated.

To address these gaps, we used multiplex immunostaining to confirm for the first time that PD-L1 is expressed by subsets of LN LECs in human melanoma-draining LNs, particularly on fLECs and mLECs, while subcapsular sinus ceiling LECs (cLECs) exhibited minimal to no PD-L1 expression. Furthermore, we comprehensively charted the immunological changes following lymphatic PD-L1 deletion within the tdLNs and primary tumors of ICB-sensitive and -resistant melanoma models in mice. By employing multidimensional flow cytometry analysis, we mapped the immune landscape of CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells, B cells and innate myeloid cells infiltrating the tdLNs and tumors. While the deletion of lymphatic PD-L1 did not affect tumor growth or progression, we observed changes in the T cell infiltrate exclusively in the TME of ICB-sensitive tumors, including expansion of PD-1⁺ CD8⁺ T_{pex} and reduction of PD-1^{hi} Th1 cells, suggestive of an improved anti-tumor T cell response. Thus, this study provides new insights into how lymphatic PD-L1 influences anti-tumor immunity and may impact to the outcome of ICB therapy in melanoma.

Results

PD-L1 is expressed by fLECs and mLECs in human melanoma-dLNs.

In murine LNs, constitutive PD-L1 expression by fLECs and mLECs has been demonstrated both at the RNA and protein levels under steady state and pathological conditions. In line with this, single-cell RNA sequencing of metastasis-free LNs from cancer patients has confirmed PD-L1 transcripts in mLEC and fLECs.^{28,29} However, lymphatic PD-L1 expression on the protein level in human LNs has not been demonstrated so far. Therefore, we established a multiplex immunofluorescence staining panel to detect lymphatic PD-L1 expression in tdLNs of melanoma patients (Fig. 1A). We included PROX1 as a pan-LEC marker, CD73 (NT5E) as a specific cLEC marker and podoplanin (D2-40) as another marker broadly expressed by peripheral LECs.²⁸ In addition, we stained for PRAME, a melanoma marker, to detect metastasis. PROX1+ nuclei were clearly distinguishable in LNs obtained from a small cohort of melanoma patients (N=3, Supplementary Table 2, Fig. 1A). Interestingly, we noticed that many LECs expressed neither CD73 nor podoplanin, whereas some LECs were single or double-positive. Of note, CD73 faithfully stained cLECs in the subcapsular sinus (SCS) region, but was not a reliable cLEC marker across the whole LN. Considerable heterogeneity could be observed even within individual sinuses, where some LECs expressed podoplanin while others were CD73+, even deep in the LN cortex (Fig. 1A). Mirroring the expression pattern of CD73 and podoplanin, PD-L1 expression exhibited considerable heterogeneity among LECs, showing distinct PD-L1 expression across individual LECs even within the same lymphatic structure (indicated by white arrows, Fig. 1A).

For quantification, LEC nuclei were selected based on PROX1 staining in either the whole LN cross-section or in the subcapsular sinus region only (Fig. 1B-C), and an expanded area around these nuclei was used as proxy for the LEC cell body. We then classified LECs into four phenotypic subsets based on the expression of CD73 and podoplanin and subsequently determined the mean fluorescence intensity of PD-L1 within each of these subsets. No significant difference in normalized PD-L1 staining intensity could be detected among the 4 LEC subsets when the entire available LN area was taken into account, although 2 out of 3 LNs showed much lower PD-L1 expression in CD73+ podoplanin- LECs (Fig. 1B). In contrast, within the SCS, PD-L1 expression was consistently observed in fLECs that were double-negative for CD73 and podoplanin, whereas CD73+ podoplanin- cLECs showed much lower PD-L1 expression. Intensity-based quantification across all 3 patients confirmed that cLECs (CD73+ podoplanin-) within the SCS significantly exhibited lower normalized PD-L1 staining intensity compared to the CD73- subsets (Fig. 1C). In conclusion, these data demonstrate for the first time that PD-L1 is expressed by LECs in human melanoma-dLNs at the protein level, with CD73+ cLECs exhibiting low to no PD-L1 in contrast to fLECs and other LECs in the LN cortex, in line with the expression pattern of PD-L1 in murine LN LECs.

Lymphatic PD-L1 deletion does not influence melanoma growth or progression in mice.

Having confirmed that LN LECs express PD-L1 in melanoma patients, we next examined the role of LEC-expressed PD-L1 in tumor immunity using clinically relevant mouse models of melanoma. To this end, we selected three syngeneic melanoma models

carrying mutations commonly found in human melanoma: YUMM5.2^{BrafV600E/wt, P53^{-/-}}, YUMM1.7^{BrafV600E/wt, Pten^{-/-}, Cdkn2a^{-/-}}, and YUMMER1.7^{BrafV600E/wt, Pten^{-/-}, Cdkn2a^{-/-}}. YUMMER1.7, being derived from YUMM1.7 through UV-induced somatic hypermutation, has been described as ICB-sensitive due to increased mutational burden, whereas YUMM1.7 and YUMM5.2 are completely ICB-resistant.^{21,22} Consequently, this panel of melanoma models allowed us to assess the impact of lymphatic PD-L1 across distinct ICB-responsiveness settings, mimicking clinical diversity regarding ICB outcomes in melanoma. Tumor cells were injected intradermally in both flanks of tamoxifen-treated PD-L1^{fl/fl} x Prox1-Cre-ER^{T2} mice (PDL1^{LECKO} mice), and tumor growth was monitored until the first mouse reached a tumor volume of 1 cm³ (Fig. 2A). Flow cytometry confirmed effective PD-L1 deletion on LN LECs at the study endpoint, without affecting their frequency (Fig. 2B, S1A-B). Notably, similar to our previous results using the B16-F10 melanoma model²⁰, deletion of LN LEC-expressed PD-L1 did not affect primary tumor growth in any of the melanoma models tested (Fig. 2C). Next, we investigated the occurrence of metastasis in the respective tdLNs of each melanoma model using an antibody against the BRAFV600E mutation of the YUMM cell lines, in combination with CD45 (Fig. 2D-E). Among the models, YUMM5.2 exhibited the highest metastatic burden, whereas YUMM1.7 and YUMMER1.7 cell lines showed similar, lower levels. Deletion of LEC-expressed PD-L1 did not alter the occurrence of tdLN metastasis in any of the models (Fig. 2D).

Lymphatic PD-L1 deletion increases proliferative PD-1+ T_{pex} cells within YUMMER1.7 tumors.

To characterize the immune landscape in tdLNs and primary tumors following targeted lymphatic deletion of PD-L1, we collected these tissues at the study endpoint and

performed in-depth flow cytometry analysis. Initially, we manually gated CD8⁺ and CD4⁺ T cell populations in tdLNs and primary tumors (Fig. 3A, S2A). In YUMMER1.7 tumors, PD-L1 deletion in LN LECs resulted in a reduced frequency of tumor-infiltrating CD8⁺ T cells compared to Cre- control mice, whereas no changes were observed in the other melanoma models (Fig. 3A). Despite this decrease, YUMMER1.7 tumors still exhibited the highest overall proportion of CD8⁺ T cells among the models. Moreover, deletion of LEC-expressed PD-L1 did not alter CD8⁺ or CD4⁺ T cell frequencies in tdLNs, nor CD4⁺ T cells in the TME (Fig. 3A).

To deeply dissect the T cell composition in tdLNs and primary tumors after lymphatic PD-L1 deletion, we applied unsupervised clustering to a multicolor flow cytometry panel of CD8⁺ T cells, which included markers of T cell subsets, activation and exhaustion states. In tdLNs, we identified 11 clusters of CD8⁺ T cells (Fig. 3B-C). Across all melanoma models, the dominant clusters of CD8⁺ T cells were a stem-like T cell cluster (cluster 2) and two naïve CD8⁺ T cell clusters (cluster 3 and 4) (Fig. 3C-D, S2B). Notably, YUMMER1.7-dLNs tended to harbor a higher proportion of proliferating CD44⁺ PD-1⁺ T cells (cluster 1) compared with the other models. However, the difference was not statistically significant.

Within the TME, we identified 12 infiltrating CD8⁺ T cell clusters (Fig. 3E-F). In primary YUMMER1.7 tumors, the frequency of proliferating PD-1⁺ T_{pex} cells (cluster 1) significantly increased following lymphatic PD-L1 deletion (Fig. 3G-H). Additionally, a PD-1^{hi} Tox^{hi} cluster of exhausted T cells (cluster 10) was considerably increased in the TME of YUMMER1.7 tumors compared to the other models but was not affected by lymphatic PD-L1 deletion (Fig. S2C). These findings suggest that lymphatic PD-L1 deletion in the YUMMER1.7 model might promote LN exit or proliferation of PD-1⁺ T_{pex} cells, facilitating

their migration into the TME where they differentiate into exhausted T cells. Alternatively, tumor-associated LECs expressing PD-L1 might reduce T_{pex} proliferation within the TME. However, these changes in the TME T cell landscape were not sufficient to reduce primary tumor growth. On the other hand, T cells in ICB-resistant melanomas were not at all affected by lymphatic PD-L1 deletion.

Lymphatic PD-L1 deletion reduces PD-1^{hi} Th1 cells in the TME of ICB-sensitive melanoma.

LECs have been shown to express MHC-I molecules and influence self-reactive and tumor-specific CD8+ T cells.^{10,20} Besides, LECs also express MHC-II molecules, although it remains unclear whether they can load peptides themselves or instead acquire peptide–MHC-II complexes from other cells.^{13,23,24} Nonetheless, previous studies have indicated that the MHC-II expression by LECs leads to CD4+ T cell dysfunction by hindering their proliferation and survival and to activation of regulatory T cells (Tregs).^{13,24} Therefore, we investigated whether lymphatic PD-L1 deletion affected CD4+ T cell populations in tdLNs and primary tumors. In tdLNs, projection and unsupervised clustering of the CD4+ T cells resulted in 10 distinct clusters, including a dominant naïve CD4+ T cell cluster (cluster 1) that did not show polarization towards any defined CD4+ Th subset (Fig. 4A-B). Neither this nor any other cluster was affected by lymphatic PD-L1 deletion (Fig. 4C, S2D). In contrast, in the TME, unsupervised clustering of infiltrating CD4+ T cells resulted in 10 clusters with Foxp3+ Tregs (cluster 3, 5, 6, 8, 9, and 10) and a PD-1^{hi} Th1 T cells (cluster 7) representing the dominant CD4+ T cell population (Fig. 4D-F, S2E). Interestingly, in YUMMER1.7 tumors, lymphatic PD-L1 deletion led to a significant reduction of this PD-1^{hi} Th1 T cell cluster (cluster 7) (Fig. 4F-G). This finding suggests a

potential role of lymphatic PD-L1 in the maintenance of PD-1^{hi} Th1 cells within the TME. However, reduction of PD-1^{hi} Th1 cells upon lymphatic PD-L1 deletion did not translate into significant effects on primary tumor growth.

Lymphatic PD-L1 deletion does not affect the myeloid and B cell populations in tdLNs and the TME.

In addition to T cells, LNs contain abundant B cell populations and diverse myeloid cell subsets. While some immune cells are resident within the LNs, many migrate from peripheral tissues to dLNs, where they play crucial roles in initiating and regulating adaptive immune responses. Recent evidence indicated that PD-1 is expressed by B cell and myeloid cell populations.²⁵⁻²⁷ This suggests that PD-L1 expressed by LECs could in principle modulate the activities of various immune cell types beyond T cells. Therefore, we analyzed B cell and myeloid cell populations in tdLNs and primary tumors of ICB-sensitive and -resistant melanoma models to determine whether lymphatic PD-L1 deletion affects their composition or phenotype. Upon lymphatic PD-L1 deletion, the frequency of myeloid cells in the tdLNs and primary tumor was not affected (Fig. S3A-B). Similarly, whereas in-depth flow cytometry analysis using unsupervised clustering of CD11b+ and/or CD11c+ myeloid cells from tdLNs and primary tumors indicated that the YUMMER1.7 TME is abundantly infiltrated by granulocytes (cluster 4), no differences following lymphatic PD-L1 depletion were noted (Fig. S3C-H).

Similar to innate myeloid cells, the overall B cell population in tdLNs and the TME was unaffected by lymphatic PD-L1 depletion (Fig. S4A-B). Unsupervised clustering of the CD19+ B cell landscape of tdLNs defined 10 clusters with a main B cell cluster expressing high levels of activation markers (CD80, CD86) and MHC-II (Fig. S4C-D). However, none

of the B cell clusters were altered upon lymphatic PD-L1 deletion (Fig. S4E). Within the TME, the B frequencies were too low for a deeper analysis (Fig. S4B). Collectively, these results indicate that lymphatic PD-L1 does not influence the composition or phenotypic distribution of myeloid or B cell populations within tdLNs or primary tumors.

Discussion

In this study, we confirmed PD-L1 expression by LECs in human melanoma-draining LNs, suggesting that lymphatic PD-L1 is relevant for tumor immunity and ICB outcomes in melanoma patients. We found consistent PD-L1 expression by fLECs and more heterogeneous expression by LECs in the LN cortex while cLECs showed minimal PD-L1 staining. However, our quantification approach has limitations, as no single marker included in the panel reliably labeled the cell body of all LECs. While Prox1 staining allowed very specific identification of LEC nuclei, the elongated morphology of LECs means that we presumably quantified only a fraction of the PD-L1 staining belonging to each of these cells. Furthermore, robust markers to distinguish LEC subsets in human LNs are missing. CD73 has been proposed as a cLEC marker²⁸, but while cLECs stained efficiently, numerous lymphatic LECs in the LN parenchyma were also CD73+, complicating the subset assignment of individual LECs. Similarly, podoplanin, which effectively stains LECs in skin and other tissues, showed discontinuous, patchy staining in LNs. To accurately quantify PD-L1 expression across distinct LEC subsets in human LN sections, the identification of reliable subset-specific LEC markers will be essential. To better understand the functional relevance of lymphatic PD-L1, we deeply and comprehensively characterized the immune landscape of tdLNs and primary tumors in

ICB-sensitive (YUMMER1.7) and -resistant (YUMM1.7, YUMM5.2) melanoma models following genetic deletion of lymphatic PD-L1. Although the loss of lymphatic PD-L1 did not reduce primary melanoma growth or metastasis, we observed a significant impact on the tumor T cell infiltrate exclusively in the ICB-sensitive YUMMER1.7 model, characterized by an accumulation of proliferating PD-1+ CD8+ T_{pex}, and by a reduction of PD-1^{hi}Th1 cells.

Early-stage CD8+ T cells in tdLNs, particularly stem-like (CD62L+ TCF1+ TOX-) and T_{pex} cells (TCF1+ TOX+), have been identified as key mediators of ICB efficacy by maintaining a pool of tumor-infiltrating exhausted T cells in the TME.^{3,8,30,31} Our observations suggest that lymphatic PD-L1 significantly inhibits such T_{pex} cells emigrating from LNs to reach the TME, in particular in “hot”, ICB-sensitive melanoma with high mutational burden and copious tumor-associated antigens available for recognition. In ICB-resistant melanoma, lymphatic PD-L1 does not exert a significant regulatory role on tumor immunity, perhaps because tumor-associated antigens are scarce and presentation by LN LECs limited.

Notably, the CD8+ T cell composition in tdLNs was not significantly altered by lymphatic PD-L1 deletion. This may reflect limitations in our ability to identify tumor-specific T cells, due to the lack of specific tumor antigen markers. Previous work by Cousin et al. demonstrated that lymphatic PD-L1 promotes apoptosis of antigen-specific T_{cm} cells in tdLNs, raising the possibility that such effects were masked within the entire CD8+ T cell pool included in our analysis.

Interestingly, YUMMER1.7-dLNs contained a higher proportion of proliferating PD-1+ CD8+ T_{pex} cells compared with the other models, suggesting that tdLNs may harbor a reservoir of effective T cells whose migration to the tumor microenvironment could be

restrained by lymphatic PD-L1. A robust pool of proliferating T_{pex} cells in tdLNs may represent a potential biomarker for ICB responsiveness. However, whether lymphatic PD-L1 limits the recruitment to the TME by interfering with the migration or the expansion of these T_{pex} cells could not be addressed in our study. Future experiments should address the origin and trafficking of proliferating PD-1+ T_{pex} cells in the TME and define the contribution of lymphatic PD-L1 to their expansion and migration.

Our data revealed a reduction in a PD-1^{hi} Th1 subset following lymphatic PD-L1 deletion within the primary tumor of the ICB-sensitive YUMMER1.7 model in contrast to the ICB-resistant models. For LECs to directly modulate CD4+ T cells, they must present loaded and functional MHC-II molecules. Although the mechanism by which LECs acquire MHC-II molecules is not entirely clear, previous studies have shown that LECs can impair CD4+ T cell proliferation and survival^{13,24}. Moreover, IFN- γ , a cytokine reported to be abundant in the YUMMER1.7 TME due to high CD8+ T cell infiltration³², can induce MHC-II upregulation on LECs.²⁴ However, the specific role of lymphatic PD-L1 in regulating PD-1^{hi} Th1 cells could not be clarified in our study.

PD-L1 is constitutively expressed at high levels by LN LECs and therefore directly affected by the conditional KO of PD-L1 under the Prox1 promoter. In contrast, peripheral LECs, such as dermal LECs, typically lack PD-L1 but can upregulate its expression in response to IFN- γ stimulation as observed in tumor-associated lymphatic vessels.^{18,19} Torphy et al. have previously shown that lymphatic vessels are present in the primary tumors of YUMMER1.7 and YUMM1.7 melanoma models.³³ In contrast, Karakousi et al. suggested markedly fewer or even absent intratumoral lymphatic vessels in YUMMER1.7 compared with YUMM1.7.³² In our flow cytometry data, tumor-associated LECs were rare, preventing direct assessment of PD-L1 deletion in this population. Nevertheless, we

cannot exclude the possibility that tamoxifen treatment induces lymphatic PD-L1 deletion on tumor-associated LECs and thereby directly influences immune cell changes in the TME. Previous work has demonstrated that YUMMER1.7-associated lymphatic vessels express higher levels of PD-L1 than those in the YUMM1.7 model or another ICB-resistant melanoma model (B16-F10).¹⁹ However, LECs are generally rare within the TME, making immunologically relevant contacts within T cells other than those exiting the TME via lymphatics rather unlikely. Nonetheless, while PD-L1 expression on tumor cells has limited predictive value as a biomarker for ICB efficacy, future studies should address whether the level of PD-L1 expression by tumor-associated LECs have predictive value in human cancers.

Methods and Materials

Sex as a biological variable: Male mice were used to match the sex of the tumor cell lines.

Mice: PD-L1^{LECKO} mice, generated by crossing PD-L1^{fl^{ox}} mice³⁴ backcrossed to a C57BL/6N background with Prox1-Cre-ER^{T2} mice³⁵, have been described previously.²⁰ Cre-mediated recombination was initiated by treating 7 weeks old mice with tamoxifen (50 mg/kg) in sunflower oil for five consecutive days intraperitoneally. Cre- littermate mice served as controls and were equally injected with tamoxifen. The mice had free access to food and drinking water.

Tumor models: Three days after the last injection, mice were intradermally injected with tumor cells. The following cell numbers were injected intradermally in both flanks: 2×10^5 YUMM1.7 and YUMM5.2 cells, and 2×10^6 YUMMER1.7 cells, in a volume of 25 μ L of PBS.

Mice were monitored three times per week, with tumor growth assessed through caliper measurements. Mice were euthanized when tumors reached a volume of 1 cm³.

Cell lines: YUMMER1.7 cells²¹ were kindly provided by Prof. Cornelia Halin (Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Zurich, Zurich, Switzerland), and the YUMM1.7 and YUMM5.2 cell lines³⁶ were generously provided by Prof. Jonathan Sleeman (Medical Faculty Mannheim, Heidelberg University, Mannheim, Germany). All cell lines were cultured in DMEM/F12 media supplemented with 1% non-essential amino acids and 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS).

Tissue processing: Tumor-draining inguinal and axillary LNs, along with primary tumors from both flanks of the mice, were collected. One inguinal LN was cryopreserved for immunofluorescence analysis while the remaining LNs were prepared for flow cytometry analysis. To process the LNs, the capsule was disrupted using a needle followed by enzymatic digestion in a solution containing 1 mg/mL Collagenase type IV (Thermo) and 40 µg/mL DNase I (Roche) in DMEM supplemented with 2% FBS, 1.2 mM CaCl₂ at 37°C for 20 minutes. After this first digestion, the supernatant was collected, and the residual LN fragments underwent a second digestion using 3.5 mg/mL Collagenase type IV and 40 µg/mL DNase I in DMEM supplemented with 2% FCS, 1.2 mM CaCl₂ at 37°C for 15 minutes. The resulting cell suspensions were passed through a cell strainer and resuspended in FACS buffer (1% FBS, 1 mmol/L EDTA, and 0.02% NaN₃ in PBS) with anti-CD16/CD32 (BioLegend 101302) and kept on ice.

For tumor processing, the tumor tissue was minced and enzymatically digested with 3.5 mg/mL Collagenase type IV and 40 µg/mL DNase I in DMEM supplemented with 2% FCS, 1.2 mM CaCl₂ at 37°C for 30 minutes. The digested tumors were filtered and passed through a 40µm cell strainer, and the cell suspension was subjected to an erythrocyte

lysis buffer (0.15 mol/L NH₄Cl, 0.01 mol/L KHCO₃, 0.1 mmol/L Na₂EDTA). Finally, cells were resuspended in FACS buffer with anti-CD16/CD32 and kept on ice.

Flow Cytometry: Cell suspensions were stained with surface antibodies (see Suppl. Table 1) in 50 µL of Brilliant Stain Buffer (BD) for an hour on ice. Following surface staining, cells were fixed and permeabilized overnight using the Foxp3 Transcription Factor Staining Buffer Set (Thermo) for intracellular staining (see Suppl. Table 1). Data acquisition was performed using a NothernLight instrument (Cytex), and data analysis using FlowJo v10.10.0 (BD).

High-parametric flow cytometry data analysis, including projection and clustering, was conducted as described by Ingelfinger et al.³⁷ Unmixed flow cytometry data were compensated in FlowJo, and immune cell populations (CD3+CD8+, CD3+CD4+, CD3-CD19+, and CD11b+ and/or CD11c+) were gated manually. Whenever possible, 10,000 cells per sample were exported. If fewer were available, all cells were included. Exported cell populations were analyzed in R (v4.4.2). The CyCombine package was used to merge data from the different mouse model experiments. Prior to dimensionality reduction, data were arcsinh-transformed and normalized to a 0-1 range. Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) was applied for visualization and unsupervised clustering was performed using the FlowSOM algorithm. The number of clusters was determined based on the marker projection within the UMAP to ensure relevant clustering. Data visualization was carried out using the ggplot2 package and statistical tests using Student's t-test analysis.

Immunofluorescence staining and analysis of tdLNs (mouse): LNs were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde for 2 hours, washed once in PBS, and incubated overnight in 30% sucrose before being embedded in OCT compound (Tissue-Tek) and cryopreserved at -

80°C. Tissue sections of 7 µm were fixed using acetone and 80% methanol following by rehydration in PBS. For staining, sections were incubated for one hour in a blocking solution containing 5% donkey serum, 1% bovine serum albumin (BSA), 0.05% NaN₃, and 0.1% Triton X-100 in PBS. Primary antibodies were then applied for an hour in the same blocking solution. The primary antibodies used were rabbit anti-BRAFV600E (Thermo MA5-24661) and anti-CD45-biotin (BioLegend 103104). After washing, sections were incubated for an hour with the secondary antibodies: donkey anti-rabbit-AF594, streptavidin-AF488 (BioLegend 405235) and Hoechst33342 (Thermo) in PBS. Sections were then washed, mounted and imaged using an AXIO Scan.7 (Zeiss). To quantify BRAFV600E+ metastatic areas in YUMM5.2-, YUMM1.7-, and YUMMER1.7-dLNs, multiple LN sections spaced approximately 100 µm apart were stained for CD45 and BRAFV600E. Naïve LNs were used as control. Merged immunofluorescence channels were used to identify CD45-/BRAFV600E+ cell clusters. From the metastatic regions manually outlined, a particle analysis was performed, and the results were normalized to the dimensions of a pre-defined region of interest (ROI) covering the whole LN cross-section.

Multiplex imaging of FFPE human melanoma-dLNs:

FFPE sections of metastatic, melanoma-draining LNs collected from 3 patients at the Department of Pathology, TU Munich were dewaxed and rehydrated, following epitope retrieval with EDTA or citrate buffer, respectively. Multiplex fluorescence staining was performed using the Phenocycler instrument (Akoya Bioscience) using rabbit anti-Prox1 (Abcam ab199359), mouse anti-podoplanin (Agilent M3619), rabbit anti-PRAME (Cell Signaling 56426), rabbit anti-NT5E (Cell Signaling 13160) and rabbit anti-PD-L1 (Cell Signaling 13684), followed by corresponding OPAL detection reagents.

Images were analyzed using QuPath. A ROI including the total LN area excluding metastasis regions and the SCS area were selected. Then, LECs were identified by detecting Prox1+ nuclei using a defined fluorescence intensity threshold specific to that LN section. A 2 μm perimeter was then expanded around each detected nucleus to include the surrounding cytoplasmic area. Nucleus detection parameters were set to a minimum area of 1 μm^2 , a maximum area of 1000 μm^2 , and a sigma value of 2 μm . For each Prox1+ event, the mean fluorescence intensity of all relevant channels was exported. In R, exported values were classified into LEC subsets based on CD73 and podoplanin (D2-40) intensity, with thresholds for each marker defined separately for every LN section. PD-L1 mean expression values were normalized to the double-negative (DN, CD73- podoplanin-) subset and then analyzed across subsets using GraphPad Prism.

Statistics: GraphPad Prism (v10.2.3) and R (v4.4.2) were utilized for statistical tests. The statistical test performed for each experiment and results are included in the figure legends. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Study approval: The responsible regional authorities (Regierungspräsidium Karlsruhe, permit G-177/22) approved all animal experiments in this study.

The use of human samples in this study was approved by the TUM Ethics Committee (approval number: 2022-140-1-S-KH).

Figure 1. PD-L1 expression by LN LECs in human melanoma-dLNs.

A. Representative microscopy images of immunofluorescence staining for CD73 (red), PROX1 (green), PD-L1 (pink), podoplanin (D2-40, light blue), PRAME (yellow) and nuclei (blue) in a human melanoma-draining LN. Blowups show a representative area of the subcapsular sinus (SCS) and the medullary region (Med). **B.** Immunofluorescence images of tdLNs from 3 individual melanoma patients stained as in (A) with corresponding quantification of PD-L1 mean fluorescence intensity in the total LN area (red lines) by CD73 and podoplanin defined subsets of Prox1+ LECs in each sample separately (bottom left panels) and combined after intensity normalization to the double-negative (DN) subset, N=2092-14218 cells/group. **C.** Images and quantification as in (B), but limited to the SCS area (yellow line), N=676-2265 cells/group. * P < 0.05; ** P < 0.01, *** P < 0.001; ****, P ≤ 0.0001; ns: non-significant; podo: podoplanin; one-way ANOVA with Sidak post-test.

Figure 2.

Figure 2. Lymphatic PD-L1 does not affect melanoma tumor growth or metastasis in tdLNs.

A. Study design overview. PDL1^{LECKO} mice were treated with tamoxifen for five consecutive days before being inoculated intradermally with syngeneic melanoma cells (indicated by

the arrow). Mice were sacrificed when the tumor volume reached 1 cm³. **B.** Frequency of LECs (CD45- Podoplanin+ CD31+) and geometrical mean fluorescence intensity (gMFI) of PD-L1 in the YUMMER1.7-, YUMM1.7- and YUMM5.2-dLNs of PD-L1^{LECKO} mice treated with tamoxifen. **C.** Tumor growth curve of YUMMER1.7, YUMM1.7, and YUMM5.2 in PD-L1^{LECKO} mice treated with tamoxifen. Tumor growth was monitored by caliper measurements. N = 3-7 mice/group. **D.** Quantification of metastatic areas in naïve and melanoma-draining LNs. N = 3-7 LNs/group. Dashed line represents background staining obtained using naïve LNs. **E.** Representative microscopy images of immunofluorescence staining for BRAFV600E (red), CD45 (green), and nuclei (blue) of LNs draining the indicated melanoma mouse models. Only the Cre- group is shown. Arrows indicate metastatic nodules.

Figure 3.

Figure 3. Lymphatic PD-L1 deletion increases proliferating PD-1+ CD8+ T cells exclusively in ICB-sensitive melanoma.

A. Frequency of CD8+ and CD4+ T cells in the primary tumors and tdLNs of YUMMER1.7, YUMM1.7 and YUMM5.2 melanoma models. N = 3-7 mice/group. * P < 0.05; one-way

ANOVA with Sidak post-test. **B.** UMAP with unsupervised clustering of CD8+ T cells in the tdLNs and individual UMAP plots for each model and condition. **C.** Heatmap depicting mean marker expression across all clusters. **D.** Frequency of clusters 1 to 4 in tdLNs. N=3-7 mice/group with 10.000 cells/mouse. **E.** UMAP with unsupervised clustering of CD8+ T cells in the TME and individual UMAP for each model and condition. **F.** Heatmap depicting mean marker expression across all clusters. **G.** Frequency of cluster 1 in the TME. N=3-7 mice/group with 1233-10.000 cells/mouse. ** P < 0.01; Student's t-test. **H.** Frequency of Ki67+ CD62L+ PD-1+ Ly6C- CD8+ T cells in YUMMER1.7, YUMM1.7 and YUMM5.2 primary tumor determined by classic flow cytometry gating. N=3-7 mice/group. ** P < 0.01; two-way ANOVA with Sidak post-test. TdLN: tumor-draining lymph node; TME: tumor microenvironment; GZM B: granzyme B; APO: Apotracker; T_{pex}: progenitor exhausted T cell; T_{ex}: exhausted T cell.

Figure 4.

Figure 4. Lymphatic PD-L1 deletion reduces PD-1⁺ Th1 cells in the YUMMER1.7 primary tumor specifically.

A. UMAP with unsupervised clustering of CD4⁺ T cells in the tdLNs and individual UMAP for each melanoma model and condition. **B.** Heatmap depicting mean marker expression across all clusters. **C.** Frequency of cluster 1 in the tdLNs. N=3-7 mice/group with 10.000 cells/mouse. **D.** UMAP with unsupervised clustering of CD4⁺ T cells in the TME and individual UMAP for each melanoma model and condition. **E.** Heatmap depicting mean

marker expression across all clusters. **F.** Frequency of cluster 7 in the TME. N=3-7 mice/group with 784-10.000 cells/mouse. * P < 0.05; Student's t-test. **G.** Frequency of PD-1+ CD44+ FOXP3- CTLA4- CD4+ T cells in YUMMER1.7, YUMM1.7 and YUMM5.2 primary tumor determined by classic flow cytometry gating. N=3-7 mice/group. * P < 0.05; two-way ANOVA with Sidak post-test. APO: Apotracker; Tregs: regulatory T cells; TdLN: tumor-draining lymph node; TME: tumor microenvironment.

Supplementary figures

Supplementary figure 1.

Supplementary figure 1.

A. Representative gating strategy used to identify LECs illustrated for a YUMMER1.7-dLN.

B. Representative histogram of PD-L1 expression on LN LECs for a Cre- and Cre+ mouse in each of the three melanoma models. TdLN: tumor-draining lymph node.

Supplementary figure 2.

Supplementary figure 2.

A. Gating strategy used to identify CD4+ and CD8+ T cells illustrated for a YUMMER1.7-dLN and primary tumor. TdLN: tumor-draining lymph node; TME: tumor microenvironment. **B.** Frequency of CD8+ T cell clusters (5 to 11) in the tdLNs. N=3-7 mice/group with 10.000 cells/mouse. **C.** CD8+ T cell cluster frequency in the TME for cluster 2 to 12. N=3-7 mice/group with 1233-10.000 cells/mouse. **D.** Frequency of CD4+ T cell clusters (2 to 10) in the tdLNs. N=3-7 mice/group with 10.000 cells/mouse. **E.**

Frequency of CD4+ T cell clusters except cluster 7 in the TME. N=3-7 mice/group with 784-10.000 cells/mouse.

Supplementary figure 3.

Supplementary figure 3.

A. Gating strategy used to identify CD11b⁺ and/or CD11c⁺ myeloid cells illustrated for a YUMMER1.7-dLN and primary tumor. **B.** Frequency of CD11b⁺ and/or CD11c⁺ myeloid cells in the tdLNs and primary tumors of YUMMER1.7, YUMM1.7 and YUMM5.2 melanoma models. N = 3-7 mice/group. ns: non-significant; one-way ANOVA with Sidak post-test. **C.** UMAP and unsupervised clustering of CD11b⁺/CD11c⁺ myeloid cells in the tdLNs and individual cluster plots for each model and condition. **D.** Heatmap representing the mean marker expression across all clusters. **E.** CD11b⁺/CD11c⁺ cell cluster frequency in melanoma-dLNs. N=3-7 mice/group with 10.000 cells/mouse. **F.** UMAP and unsupervised clustering of CD11b⁺/CD11c⁺ cells in the TME and individual cluster plots for each model and condition. **G.** Heatmap representing the mean marker expression across all clusters. **H.** CD11b⁺/CD11c⁺ cell cluster frequency in TME. N=3-7 mice/group with 10.000 cells/mouse. TdLN: tumor-draining lymph node; TME: tumor microenvironment; ARG: arginase; MΦ: macrophage; DCs: dendritic cells; pDCs: plasmacytoid dendritic cells.

Supplementary figure 4.

Supplementary figure 4.

A. Gating strategy used to identify CD19⁺ B cells illustrated for a YUMMER1.7-dLN and primary tumor. **B.** Frequency of CD19⁺ B cells in the tdLNs and primary tumors of each indicated melanoma model. ns=non-significant; one-way ANOVA with Sidak post-test. **C.** UMAP and unsupervised clustering of CD19⁺ B cells in the tdLNs and individual cluster plots for each indicated melanoma-dLN and condition. **D.** Heatmap representing the mean marker expression across all clusters. **E.** CD19⁺ B cell cluster frequency in

melanoma-dLNs. N=3-7 mice/group with 10.000 cells/mouse. * P < 0.05; ** P < 0.01; Student's t-test. TdLN: tumor-draining lymph node; TME: tumor microenvironment; GC: germinal center.

Supplementary Table 1. List of antibodies used for flow cytometry.

Supplementary Table 2. Patient characteristics.

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